

Virginia state record of *Phyciodes phaon* (W. H. Edwards, 1864) (Nymphalidae: Limenitidinae).

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ABSTRACT: A state record specimen of *Phyciodes phaon*, originally reported by the author in the Virginia Butterfly Bulletin (Pavulaan, 2000), is illustrated for the first time with a view of location collected.

INTRODUCTION

Phyciodes phaon (Phaon Crescent) is a common species of the coastal region of southeastern United States and peninsular Florida. It has been recorded along the North Carolina coast as far north as the Outer Banks (LeGrand & Howard, 2021). The hostplant along the southeast coast is *Phyla nodiflora* (Frogfruit).

OBSERVATIONS

On Little Island City Beach in Virginia Beach, VA, 10 Sep 2000, along a weedy strip between Sandpiper Road and Little Island Beach parking lot (**Fig. 1**), I collected a male *Phyciodes phaon* (**inset**), a state record.

Fig. 1. Habitat in Virginia Beach, VA, where *Phyciodes phaon* (**inset**) was collected, 10 Sep 2000.

REFERENCES

- LeGrand, Jr., H. E. & T. E. Howard, Jr. 2021. Butterflies of North Carolina. Twenty-eighth Approximation. https://auth1.dpr.ncparks.gov/nbnc/nbnc_28.php (accessed 3/18/2021).
Pavulaan, H. 2000. 2000 Spring/Summer Summary. The Virginia Butterfly Bulletin 8(4): 7-11.